

Research Article

Determination of Relationships between Yield Components in Bean by Using Path Coefficient Analysis

^{1*}Alihan Cokkizgin, ²Mustafa Colkesen, ³Leyla Idikut,
⁴Bahri Ozsisli and ⁵Umit Girgel

¹Vocational School of Higher Edition in Nurdagi, Gaziantep University, Nurdagi, Gaziantep 27840, Turkey

^{2,3,5}The Department of Field Crop, Faculty of Agriculture, Sutcu Imam University, Kahramanmaras 46050, Turkey

⁴The Department of Food Engineering, Faculty of Agriculture, Sutcu Imam University, Kahramanmaras 46050, Turkey

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ABSTRACT

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*Corresponding Author

Alihan Cokkizgin

E-mail: acokkizgin@gantep.edu.tr

This study was performed under three location conditions (Kahramanmaras-Center/Turkey, Kahramanmaras-Goksun district/Turkey and Malatya-Darende district/Turkey) in year 2008 with six common beans genotypes (Gungor, Yakutiye-98, Aras-98, Onceler-98, Goynuk-98 and a local genotype). The experiments were carried out in order to determine the relationships between seed yield and yield components. Direct and indirect effects of the yield components on seed yield were found by using Correlation and Path coefficient analysis. It was observed that seed yield was significantly correlated with all traits except plant height and 100-seed weight. On the other hand, the relationship of seed yield per plant with branch number per plant ($r=0.78$), pod length ($r=0.51$), seed number per pod ($r=0.57$), seed weight per pod ($r=0.87$), pod number per plant ($r=0.90$), seed number per plant ($r=0.88$), and seed yield per plant ($r=0.92$), was positive while correlation of seed yield per plant with first pod height ($r=-0.79$) was negative. Path analysis depicted that seed number per plant had positive and highest-direct effect ($p=2.3274$) on the seed yield while seed weight per plant had negative and highest-direct effect ($p=-0.9575$) on the seed yield.

Keywords:

Common Bean, path coefficient, correlation, yield, yield components

INTRODUCTION

Over a period of at least 7000 to 8000 years, the common bean has evolved from a wild-growing vine distributed in highlands of Middle America and Andes into major leguminous food crop, grown worldwide in a broad range of environments and cropping systems (Gepts and Debouck, 1991).

Common bean is an important component of agricultural and food systems throughout most of the world. Nutritionally dry bean is a nearly, perfect and rich food. It is an excellent source of protein, carbohydrates and fairly good source of minerals, vitamins, folic acid and dietary fiber (Rehman *et al.*, 2001).

Common bean has 25.2 million ha sowing area and 19.7 million ton total production per year in the world. On the other hand Turkey has 103.255 ha harvest area and 212.758 ton total production per year (FAO, 2010).

To achieve significant progress in breeding programs, it is essential to know the relationship between seed yield and its components (Assady *et al.*, 2005). Path coefficient analysis is used to partition the relative contribution of yield components via standardized partial regression coefficients. Correlation coefficient which measures the simple linear relationship between two traits does not predict the success of selection. However, path analysis determines the relative importance of direct and indirect effects on seed yield (Bhatt, 1973). In addition, it has been used to organize and present the casual relationships between predictor variables and response variables through a path diagram that is based on experimental results or on a priori grounds (Board *et al.*, 1997).

Path coefficient analysis has been widely used in crop breeding to determine the nature of relationships between grain yield and its contributing components and to identify those components with significant effects on yield for potential use as selection criteria (Mohammadi *et al.*, 2003).

Correlation and path coefficient have been extensively conducted in various legume crops e.g., for instance, Bingliang and Mingliang (2003), Gonçalves *et al.* (2003), Karasu and Oz (2010), Salehi *et al.* (2010) and Sadeghi *et al.* (2011) on bean, Arshad *et al.* (2002), Sagir *et al.* (2004) on chickpea, Karadavut (2009) on lentil, Ulukan *et al.* (2003) on faba bean, Hassan *et al.* (2003) on mungbean, Nawab *et al.* (2008) on pea, Dursun (2007) on bean, Malik *et al.* (2007) on soybean etc.

This study was aimed to determine the relationship among seed yield and yield components, and their direct and indirect effects of contributing characters to seed yield in common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Site Description

Six genotypes (Gungor, Yakutiye-98, Aras-98, Onceler-98, Goynuk-98 and a local genotype) of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) were grown in Kahramanmaras-City center/Turkey (Latitude 37° 58' 03" N, Longitude 36° 52' 59" E), Kahramanmaras-Goksun district/Turkey (Latitude 38° 05' 31" N, Longitude 36° 33' 53" E) and Malatya-Darende district/Turkey (Latitude 38° 31' 20" N, Longitude: 37° 33' 06" E) in 2008.

Experiment

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Each entry was planted in a plot having 4 rows of 5- meter length. The row and plant spacing's were kept 50 cm and 10 cm, respectively. Individual plot size was 2 x 5 m=10m². Fertilizer dose (2.5 kg N₂ and 6.0 kg P₂O₅ per decare) was applied at the time of planting. The experiments were subjected to the recommended cultural practices uniformly.

Measurements

Observations on plant height (cm), first pod height (cm), branch number per plant, pod length (cm), seed number per pod, seed weight per pod (g), pod number per plant, seed number per plant, seed weight per plant (g) were randomly recorded from 10 plants. Hundred-seed weight was determined for each plot from a sample of the seed harvested. Seed yield (kg da⁻¹) was determined on a plot basis and calculated to decare.

Statistical Analyses

Simple correlation coefficients between all possible combinations of variables were worked out according to Snedecor (1957) combining all environmental conditions. Path coefficient technique was performed according to the method of Wright (1921), as illustrated by Dewey and Lu (1959). In path analysis, seed yield was the dependent variable and the other characteristics were considered as independent variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Correlation Coefficient

Correlation coefficient between all possible combinations was estimated (Table 1).

Table 1: Correlation coefficients among combinations of all characters in common bean

	SY	PH	FPH	NBP	POL	NSPO	WSPO	NPOP	NSP	SYP	100SW
SY	1.00										
PH	0.10	1.00									
FPH	-0.79**	0.28	1.00								
NBP	0.78**	0.42	-0.41	1.00							
POL	0.51*	-0.36	-0.47*	0.16	1.00						
NSPO	0.57*	-0.43	-0.56*	0.45	0.57*	1.00					
WSPO	0.87**	0.24	-0.67**	0.61**	0.46	0.29	1.00				
NPOP	0.90**	0.06	-0.74**	0.79**	0.48*	0.68**	0.80**	1.00			
NSP	0.88**	-0.10	-0.71**	0.78**	0.54*	0.84**	0.67**	0.95**	1.00		
SYP	0.92**	0.10	-0.73**	0.82**	0.39	0.62**	0.84**	0.96**	0.92**	1.00	
100SW	0.39	0.52*	-0.24	0.31	-0.15	-0.28	0.67**	0.30	0.08	0.45	1.00

*, ** denotes significant at 5% and 1% probability level

SY: Seed yield, PH: Plant height, FPH: First pod height, NBP: Number of branches per plant, POL: Pod length, NSPO: Number of seeds per pod, WSPO: Weight of seeds per pod, NPOP: Number of pods per plant, NSP: Number of seed per plant, SYP Seed yield per plant, 100SY: 100-seed weight

Results indicated that all traits were highly significantly correlated with seed yield except plant height and 100-seed weight. The effects of branch number per plant ($r=0.78^{**}$), pod length ($r=0.51^*$), seed number per pod ($r=0.57^*$), seed weight per pod ($r=0.87^{**}$), pod number per plant ($r=0.90^{**}$), seed number per plant ($r=0.88^{**}$), seed yield per plant ($r=0.92^{**}$), were positive while the effects of first pod height ($r=-0.79^{**}$) on the seed yield were negative. The significant positive correlations of branches, number of pods per plant with grain yield, have also been reported by Singh *et al.*, (1999). Similar observations have been made by Togay *et al.* (2008). Seed yield per plant indicated the highest correlation value (0.92) with seed yield in comparison with other traits. These results revealed the importance of the seed yield per plant as a criterion for common bean yield improvement. These results are in agreement with Kaul *et al.* (1982), Kumar *et al.* (1983), Rajput and Sarwar (1999), Chakraborty and Haque (2000), Chauhan and Singh (2001), Kumar *et al.* (2002), Vir and Gupta (2002), Verma *et al.* (2004), Dursun (2007).

Plant height had positive and significant correlation with 100-seed weight ($r=0.52^*$). First pod height exhibited negative and significant correlation with pod length ($r=-0.47^*$), number of seeds per pod ($r=-0.56^*$), weight of seeds per pod ($r=-0.67^{**}$), number of pod per plant ($r=-0.74^{**}$), number of seeds per plant ($r=-0.74^{**}$) and seed yield per plant ($r=-0.73^{**}$).

Number of branches per plant had positive and significant correlation with weight of seeds per pod ($r=0.61^{**}$), number of pod per plant ($r=0.79^*$), number of seed per plant ($r=0.78^{**}$), seed yield per plant ($r=0.82^{**}$). Pods per plant had strong positive association with branches (Singh *et al.*, 1990; Atta *et al.*, 2008).

Pod length showed positive and significant correlation with number of seeds per pod ($r=0.57^*$), number of pod per plant ($r=0.48^*$) and number of seed per plant ($r=0.54^*$).

Number of seeds per pod had strong positive and significant relationship with number of pod per plant ($r=0.68^*$), number of seed per plant ($r=0.84^*$) and seed yield per plant ($r=0.62^*$).

Weight of seeds per pod exhibited positive and significant correlation with number of pod per plant ($r=0.80^{**}$), number of seed per plant ($r=0.67^{**}$), seed yield per plant ($r=0.84^{**}$) and 100-seed weight ($r=0.67^{**}$).

Number of pod per plant had positive and significant correlation with number of seeds per plant ($r=0.95^{**}$) and seed yield per plant ($r=0.96^{**}$).

Positive and significant correlation was observed between number of seeds per plant and seed yield per plant ($r=0.92^{**}$). Cokkizgin (2007) also reported significant positive correlation between numbers of seed per plant with seed yield per plant. All other observed relationships among yield components were not significant.

Path Coefficient

Path coefficient between all possible combinations was estimated (Table 2). The path coefficient analysis appeared to provide a clue to the contribution of various components of yield to over all seed yield in the genotypes under study. It provides an effective way of finding out direct and indirect sources of correlation. The direct contribution of number of seed per plant was highest ($p=2.3274$) followed by weight of seeds per pod ($p=0.5696$), 100-seed weight ($p=0.3180$) and number of branches per plant ($p=0.1729$) whereas seed yield per plant had maximum negative direct effect on seed yield ($p=-0.9575$) and followed by number of pods per plant ($p=-0.9116$), number of pod per plant ($p=-0.4090$), first pod height ($p=-0.1660$), pod length ($p=-0.0451$) and plant height ($p=-0.0358$). These results are in agreement with those obtained by Peksen and Gulumser (2005), Cokkizgin (2007).

Table 2: Path coefficient analysis for seed yield

Character	Direct Effect	Indirect effect									
		PH	FPH	NBP	POL	NSPO	WSPO	NPOP	NSP	SYP	100SW
PH	-0.0358		-0.0461	0.0719	0.0164	0.1744	0.1351	-0.0563	-0.2301	-0.0996	0.1656
FPH	-0.1660	-0.0100		-0.0704	0.0212	0.2302	-0.3813	0.6747	-1.7181	0.7025	-0.0770
NBP	0.1729	-0.0149	0.0676		-0.0072	-0.1845	0.3450	-0.7188	1.8048	-0.7824	0.0976
POL	-0.0451	0.0130	0.0782	0.0275		-0.2344	0.2603	-0.4377	1.2654	-0.3696	-0.0475
NSPO	-0.4090	0.0153	0.0934	0.0780	-0.0258		0.1630	-0.6207	1.9600	-0.5954	-0.0873
WSPO	0.5696	-0.0085	0.1111	0.1047	-0.0206	-0.1170		-0.7304	1.5521	-0.8062	0.2138
NPOP	-0.9116	-0.0022	0.1229	0.1364	-0.0216	-0.2785	0.4564		2.2161	-0.9183	0.0956
NSP	2.3274	0.0035	0.1225	0.1341	-0.0245	-0.3444	0.3799	-0.8680		-0.8806	0.0268
SYP	-0.9575	-0.0037	0.1218	0.1413	-0.0174	-0.2543	0.4796	-0.8742	2.1403		0.1418
100SW	0.3180	-0.0187	0.0402	0.0531	0.0067	0.1123	0.3830	-0.2740	0.1964	-0.4271	

PH: Plant height, FPH: First pod height, NBP: Number of branches per plant, POL: Pod length, NSPO: Number of seeds per pod, WSPO: Weight of seeds per pod, NPOP: Number of pods per plant, NSP: Number of seeds per plant, SYP Seed yield per plant, 100SW: 100-seed weight.

Number of pod per plant showed the highest positive indirect effect through number of seed per plant ($p=2.2161$) whereas first pod height had the highest negative indirect effect through number of seed per plant ($p=-1.7181$) on seed yield.

On the other hand, first pod height also had an appreciable indirect effect via seed yield per plant and number of pod per plant (respectively $p=0.7025$ and $p=0.6747$).

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded from the present studies that number of seeds per plant appeared to be the highest contributor to the grain yield. Therefore, direct and indirect selection for higher grain yield may be effective for improving this character, as had been shown by Peksen and Gulumser (2005), Sabokdast and Khyalparast (2008) and Atta *et al.* (2008), in various studies on legume crops. Selection for increasing seed yield through these traits might be more successful.

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